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(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Health of community people

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Abstract

Due to development of many nutraceuticals and other nutritional products people are facing huge problems in maintaining their health. People now are attracted to the food Available outside rather than homemade and naturally occurring fruits. Objective of this survey the people following natural organic food as they need regularly to maintain their health. It is based on the people who follows natural organic diet like vegetable, meat, and fruits. By taking all the reports from the people we finally came to know that people are moving forward by taking organic, natural vegetable, meat, and fruits than the marketed products available.

Keywords: Nutraceuticals; Vegetables; Meat; Fruit

1. Introduction

Industrialization leads to pollution (air, water, soil, food) due to use of many chemicals, heavy metals, and other man-made items, are the cause of many harmful diseases, physiological problems as well as other degenerative diseases. These raised the demands for health care have dramatically increased the cost of drug, consumers are turning massively to food supplements to improve their health where pharmaceuticals fails. Therefore, the scientists and researcher have forced to think about natural or alternative medicines and their application [1].

Our planet is rich with variety of plant species that possess medicinal properties. Some of these have been used since longtime for immune modulation to prevent diseases. Many people are yet eating for fast food rather than organic foods, now a days herbs are getting popularity in veterinary medicines for treating mastitis, skin allergies, food poisoning expulsion of placenta. Herbs are suitable for both human and animals. Out of 21,000 plant species listed by World Health Organisation 2500 are found in India declaring tremendous potential of the country as making largest producer of medicinal herbs.

Plants particularly the fruits are one of the most important resources of the human food and have been utilised as a natural source of medicinal compounds since thousands of years. With recent advances in medicinal and nutrition sciences, natural products and health promoting food have received extensive attention from both health professionals. New trend has appeared now phytonutrients, phytomedicines, phytotherapy is gaining importance in our daily life.[2],[3]and playing positive role in enhancing medical benefits, and further improving immune function to prevent specific disease with the promise to reduce side effects[4]. The term nutraceuticals was coined by Stephan DeFelice,

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(founder and chairman pf foundation for innovation in medicine,) at Cranford New Jersey [5]. The term “nutraceutical” combines with the word “nutrient’ (a nourishing food component) with “pharmaceutical effect” (a medical drug) in 1989 by Stephan DeFekice, (founder and chairman pf foundation for innovation in medicine,). According to DeFelice nutraceuticals can be defined as a food (or part of food) that provides medical or health benefits including the prevention and treatment of disease. Nutraceuticals may contain substances that are “natural” expressed intent of treatment or prevention of diseases but may not be generally recognised as safe [6].

2. Material and methods

In this study we have to do particular methods in that, Diet prefer regularly, Food like to eat the most, Eat fruits regularly, Prefer market nutritional products, Problems after taking market nutritional products, Juice prefer.

3. Results

In the table below there are people who are following natural organic food, meat and fruits regularly As their food to maintain their health.

Table 1 Diet prefer regularly

Food type	Total no of case	Respondents (%)
Vegetables	90	73.77
Meat	14	11.48
Fruits	10	8.20
Fast food	8	6.5

Figure 1 Bar diagram of diet prefer regularly

3.1. Food like to eat the most

Here in this people who like eating food that they like most are given below like vegetables, meat, and fast food. On their regular basis the kind of diet they follow are given below.

Table 2 Food like to eat the most

Food Type	Cases	Response (%)
Veg and Meat	50	41.32
Veg and Fast food	34	28.10
Meat and Fast food	22	18.18
Veg and Fast food	15	12.40

Figure 2 Bar diagram of Food like to eat the most

3.2. Fruits eat regularly

Most of the people do not eat fruits as to maintain their health in good way the reports shows that nearly half of the people likes to eat fruits.

Table 3 Fruits eat regularly

views	Cases	Response (%)
Yes	47	38.84
No	74	61.16

Figure 3 Fruits eat regularly

3.3. Prefer Nutritional product

Most of the people in the community are too busy with their work so nutraceutical products are made available for those people to maintain their health. The chart shows that the people who takes nutraceutical products are less than the people who takes vegetables.

Table 4 Prefer Nutritional product

Views	Cases	Response (%)
Yes	19	16.20
No	107	74.80

Figure 4 Prefer Nutritional product

3.4. Problems after taking nutritional products

Taking any kind of nutraceutical product people must consult to doctor that they need the nutraceutical product or through natural diet they can improve their health. May people without any consultant of a nutritional expert buy these products which have cause many side effects to the people.

Table 5 Problems after taking nutritional products

Views	Cases	Response (%)
Yes	5	4.1
No	14	11.48

Figure 5 Problems after taking nutritional products

3.5. During medical treatment prefer food

Mostly fruits are only preferred during medical treatment for the patient but they also eat other fruit than naturally occurring organic vegetables and fruits.

Table 6 During medical treatment prefer food.

Food type	Cases	Response (%)
Vegetables and food	31	26.72
Fruits and fruits juice	85	73.28
Other	10	8.20

Figure 6 During medical treatment prefer food.

3.6. Juice preferred

Drinking fruit juices are even preferred than eating as all the nutrition is directly given in the form of juices the reports are given below-

Table 7 Juice preferred

Food type	cases	Response (%)
Marketed	24	20.34
Homemade	94	79.66

Figure 7 Juice preferred

4. Conclusion

The final conclusion after taking all the responses of the people we came to know that people are moving forward to maintain their health by eating nutritious organic food like vegetable, meat, fruits rather than junk food and marketed products.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors should have not any conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

If studies involve information about any individual e.g. case studies, survey, interview etc., author must write statement of informed consent as “Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.”

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